

The image shows a modern industrial factory environment. In the foreground, a white robotic arm is visible, extending from a metal frame. In the background, another blue robotic arm is working on a production line. The scene is brightly lit, and the overall atmosphere is one of advanced manufacturing technology. The image is partially overlaid by a large blue geometric graphic on the right side, which consists of several overlapping triangles and quadrilaterals in various shades of blue and cyan.

smartFactory^{KL}

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SmartFactory Reference Architecture

Standardised Connection of IT and OT

Authors

Simon Jungbluth, Benjamin Blumhofer, Carsten Harms, Pascal Rübél, Simon Bergweiler,
Prof. Dr. Martin Ruskowski

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Preface

For two decades, SmartFactory^{KL} has stood for innovation, collaboration and technological foresight in the field of industrial production. During this time, we have worked with our partners to develop, test and implement forward-looking concepts.

Below, we present the SmartFactory Reference Architecture, which offers companies a clear framework for successfully responding to increasing market and technological pressures. It supports a consistent data strategy, enables the gradual modernisation of existing production environments and, through openness and scalability, creates the basis for the integration of future key technologies.

We would like to thank everyone involved and look forward to many more years of innovative collaboration.

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Introduction and Motivation

In 2022, the Manufacturing-X task force of the “Plattform Industrie 4.0” [1] described the need ‘[...] developing and establishing a decentrally organised data economy for German and European industry [...]’ [1]. The reasons for such a cross-sector industrial policy initiative include growing competitive pressure on industry (e.g. due to supply bottlenecks or the threat of a global recession) and increasing regulatory requirements (e.g. by the European Commission). The objectives are to increase the resilience of German industrial companies so that they can react quickly to disruptions and reorganise value creation networks, as well as to maintain and expand the competitive strength of German industry on the world market. For this to succeed, an intelligent and connected industry is needed. In this industry, data must be seamlessly integrated and companies must be prepared to share it securely and trustingly with each other. This requires the end-to-end networking of the entire value chain of all players. With regard to the industrial landscape in Germany, which is characterised by small and medium-sized enterprises, new challenges are emerging:

- Companies must compete in a market dominated by monopolistic platform operators,
- The necessary digital transformation requires far-reaching structural adjustments, in particular through the end-to-end networking and vertical integration of data from the shop floor to the cloud,
- The rigid, hardware-bound control systems that prevail on the shop floor must be modernised and decoupled in order to create the flexibility and resilience necessary to respond quickly to market changes,
- against the background of demographic change and the associated shortage of skilled workers, the strategic handling of knowledge and data is becoming increasingly important. Companies must secure and expand their digital knowledge base in order to effectively train future employees and support them in complex tasks with intelligent systems [2].

Based on the idea of a connected data economy, the German government launched the Manufacturing-X initiative in 2024 to improve the competitiveness of Germany/Europe [3]. This requires a common basis for data exchange. A manufacturer-independent, standardised and semantic structure of information models for the exchange of machine-readable and interpretable data (1), standardised communication for automated negotiations and data exchange (2), and a federated and secure data infrastructure in accordance with European laws (3) are now necessary [4]. Connectivity and digitalisation are key drivers in unlocking new value creation potential. To this end, assets – in our context, tangible or intangible objects of value for an organisation [5] must be described in vendor-independent and interoperable in order to enable cross-functional communication between OT and IT [6]. This is achieved by ensuring that all industrial assets and services have standardised data models and interfaces. The integration of hardware and software components can be carried out seamlessly thanks to standardised self-description, which makes both real and virtual structures more resilient.

Key Concepts in Connected Value Creation Systems

There are different interoperability solutions [7] for enabling seamless connectivity, which can be used in different life cycle phases. The Reference Architecture Model Industry 4.0 (RAMI 4.0) [8] defines a structured framework for the systematic classification of technical, organisational and semantic standards in the context of Industry 4.0. The following three standards [9] are used to integrate the shop floor level:

- *AutomationML* – for asset development and planning of productive use,
- *OPC UA* – for productive use and maintenance of the asset,
- *Asset Administration Shell (AAS)* – for communication in the connected world, and additional content (such as type plate, parts list, product carbon footprint (PCF), etc.) that can be assigned to the manufactured product.

Another key element in the creation of connected systems is secure data exchange and keeping data sovereignty. For this purpose, Gaia-X [10] provides a set of internationally applicable rules, standards and governance structures. In this context, technical concepts and protocols developed by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) [11], [12] plays a central role, particularly with regard to trustworthy data exchange, the enforcement of data usage policies, and the establishment of interoperable and federated data spaces. Initial examples of domain-specific data spaces include Catena-X [13] for the automotive industry and smartMA-X [4] for the manufacturing sector. Catena-X developed the Eclipse Dataspace Connector [14], which is based on the Gaia-X specifications and implements the IDSA Dataspace Protocol. Dataspace Protocol [12] realizes data negotiation and enables data transfer according to defined policies. In the following, the term connector is used to describe the connection to a data space. A greatly simplified representation of a data space can be seen in Figure 1.

Various companies and organisations work together in digital data spaces, often without knowing each other personally. A technical trust model is needed to ensure that this collaboration is secure and efficient. This is based on the issuer–holder–verifier principle [15]. All parties involved have their own decentralised identity (DID), which enables secure and unique identification. On this basis, each party (verifier) can decide for itself which issuers of digital credentials it trusts and which information it accepts from holders. Now that basic concepts for

trustworthy data exchange have been defined, the focus is shifting to concrete implementation: The SmartFactory Reference Architecture provides an application-oriented architecture model that enables the structural and functional networking of OT and IT systems in the factory. It thus creates the technical basis for interoperability, modularity and secure data exchange in digitalised production environments.

The Reference Architecture of the SmartFactory

The following Reference Architecture for the SmartFactory creates a basis for the seamless integration of IT and OT systems and enables end-to-end data connections from the shop floor to the connected world. The architecture is intended to show how components can be intelligently encapsulated and linked. This should give rise to new business models, accelerate innovation, shorten commissioning times, increase variant diversity and make plants more flexible. Here, it is important to protect existing investments and integrate existing applications. Figure 2 represents the components of the Reference Architecture. The Reference Architecture is divided into a well-structured three-layer model that systematically maps the individual functional levels of a factory, from the physical shop floor to the higher-level IT infrastructure. The aim of this structured layout is to map the allocation of functions, interfaces and responsibilities that support both the vertical integration and horizontal scalability of industrial systems:

OT level: This lowest layer includes field devices, sensors and actuators that interact directly with the physical production environment. It forms the basis for data acquisition and process execution.

IT/OT coupling layer: As an intermediary layer, this layer integrates edge components and controls. It enables secure, high-performance communication between operational systems and IT services and forms the interface for data aggregation, pre-processing and control.

Figure 1: Components of a dataspace

IT level: The top layer encapsulates all higher-level applications, from classic ERP and MES systems to agent-based services and AI-supported analysis modules. It represents the central instance for planning, optimisation and data-driven decision-making.

OT-IT Convergence for Smart Factories

Looking at the fieldbus level, it is clear that numerous different bus systems and protocols have developed over time. This is mainly due to the fact that different manufacturers have met the specific requirements of individual industries with their own, sometimes proprietary solutions. Conventional bus

systems are represented in the architecture by Programmable Logic Controllers (PLC) and the associated actuators and sensors. This complicates the integration of new devices into an existing production system, as it requires modifications to the embedded code that runs the factory's automation. Other type of of field devices (smart sensors and smart actuators) describe devices that operate independently and support the direct reading of information or control of actuators via defined interfaces of the edge layer. Examples include RFID sensors that provide a web interface for reading tags directly, or a robot that can runs predefined jobs using

Figure 2: Reference Architecture of the SmartFactory^{KL}

remote procedure calls. In the Reference Architecture, these smart devices are no longer integrated into a classic PLC, but into edge devices. These must meet both real-time requirements and high security standard.¹ So-called interface applications, which store the data from the individual interfaces on a digital OT data bus, are available for integration. This is where classic automation ends, as the data from the field level can now be processed independently of conventional control systems and reused in freely selectable programming languages.

This is where smart machine control (Smart Machine Logic Controller) and encapsulated automation functions – known as skills – come into play. Skills represent the executable implementation of an encapsulated automation function, enabling flexible commissioning and reconfiguration of production systems [16]. Instead of a device-centric view, field devices and machines are increasingly being viewed from a function-oriented perspective. Smart machine control wraps the proprietary interfaces of PLCs, smart sensors and smart actuators into modular skills. In addition, it is possible to access and reuse existing skills from smart machines. Based on the available skills, smart machine control derives complex, higher-value functions. On the one hand, these higher-value functions are very flexible; on the other hand, they can be easily adapted without having to modify the embedded control code. Additionally, the underlying hardware can be replaced without requiring changes to the skills.

The Smart Machine Interface processes and converts the operational data from the OT data bus into a standardised format and acts as a central access point to the machine network. We recommend OPC UA for Machinery [17], [18] for this purpose. This provides interoperable machine states, enables standardized process monitoring, and supports semantic data interpretation. The skills of the components can be made available through so-called building blocks [19]. The standardised machine interface allows the use and reuse of unified machine operating interfaces and evaluation tools. This

means that individual solutions for machine control (e.g. WinCC) no longer need to be developed. On the other hand, the standardised user interface makes it easier to operate new machines, as operators can familiarise themselves with the functions more quickly. This leads to reduced training times, fewer sources of error and an overall increase in efficiency in the production process.

Enhancing Value through Contextual Data Connectivity

Once you leave the IT/OT level, it is no longer sufficient to focus solely on operational data; instead, the entire life cycle of the assets must be taken into account. AAS acts as a central access point for all data points of an asset and enables the linking of decentralised data sources via standardised interface descriptions [20]. This creates a uniform view of heterogeneous data sets, which include static information such as master data, technical specifications or operating parameters, as well as dynamic machine data. Existing and customised applications² can be seamlessly integrated into the Reference Architecture by converting manufacturer-specific data into AAS-compliant formats, thereby enabling consistent data exchange between applications. Different data sources, such as the Smart Machine Interface and existing components, can be used to aggregate data in a standardised and automated manner. This aggregated data makes it possible to create reports that meet the requirements for transparency and traceability throughout the entire asset lifecycle.

The standardised structures of the digital IT data bus enable data to be connected directly to existing data spaces via a connector. The connector integrates into the company's existing access rights management system and grants access to authorised parties in accordance with agreed policies. This ensures trust, data sovereignty and security within the ecosystem. Thanks to the semantic description of the data, it is possible to seamlessly integrate both internal and external data sources into the company's

¹ Examples of these automation solutions include [ctrlX Automation \(Bosch Rexroth\)](#) and [Industrial Edge \(Siemens\)](#)

² Legacy and custom applications refer to all existing applications within an organisation. These include ERP, CAD and CAM

systems, as well as solutions developed specifically for the organisation.

internal data bus. This creates the basis for data-centric corporate management, where the origin of the data is irrelevant; what matters is the added value created through consistent and scalable use across system and company boundaries. This offers major advantages, especially for applications with Artificial Intelligence (AI). Access to contextually described data makes it possible to analyse AI information efficiently, recognise patterns more quickly and make informed predictions. At the same time, the unified structure reduces the effort required for pre-processing and creates a reliable foundation, making AI faster to deploy, more accurate, more transparent and scalable across the enterprise.

Smart Production Control Using AI Agents

Decentralised, autonomous entities can be integrated into the control systems of modern factories via the IT data bus as a central entry point. This requires identifying the relationships between data points, deriving decisions and pursuing production targets in line with the overall corporate strategy. To meet these requirements, we rely on autonomous intelligent entities known as agents [21]. Agents act independently and pursue a goal, but are able to cooperate with other agents.

This principle forms the basis of a production concept that is specifically designed to increase the flexibility, scalability and adaptability of manufacturing systems, for example to support product customisation or to deal with unpredictable operating conditions [22].

These agents manage individual assets (especially products and resources such as work centres, machines, manual workstations or transport units) and represent the proactive part of an asset.

We use a subdivision into Service Agents, Product Agents and Resource Agents. Service Agents coordinate cross-company data exchange through negotiating and providing services within a data space using connectors. They negotiate access to data assets based on defined policies. The Product Agent is responsible for production planning and scheduling and, in cooperation with the Resource Agent, operates on production orders. The Resource Agent is responsible for executing production orders, optimising the scheduling and utilisation of the respective machine [23], [24].

Digital Twin-Driven Manufacturing in Five Steps

The Reference Architecture presented outlines the digital structure of a self-organising factory controlled by digital twins. The vision of the self-organising factory cannot be realised with a single technological leap; it is the result of a gradual, systematically structured transformation process. Figure 3 shows how companies can move from manual processes to autonomously controlled production processes in five clearly defined stages.

Figure 3: Digital Twin-driven Manufacturing in five steps

The first step forms the basis for all further developments. Investments in digital standards and interfaces lay the foundation for the long-term flexibility and scalability of the factory. Machines, work centres and IT systems must be able to communicate with each other via uniform information models and standardised interfaces. The use of AAS and OPC UA lays the necessary foundation for consistent data availability, both vertically across system boundaries and horizontally across the shop floor. Once the basic data flows have been established, the next step is to systematically improve the quality of the data.

In the second step, reliable data serves as the basis for making informed decisions. Initial analysis functions provide a clear, data-based view of processes, bottlenecks and potential. Relevant information is provided automatically so that deviations can be identified early on and corrective measures can be initiated promptly. Analysed data can be used for automated reporting.

In the third step, the findings from the previous analyses are used to derive specific optimisation measures. Data-based process improvements can increase efficiency, reduce costs and strengthen competitiveness.

In step four, the introduction of digital agents for products and resources creates a network of autonomously interacting entities. These agents enable decentralised control. Products can communicate requirements, and resources can report their current status and availability: this forms the basis for dynamic decision-making.

In the fifth step, products and resource agents cooperate independently to implement production orders efficiently and flexibly. The factory responds to changes in real time, organises processes independently and adapts dynamically to new requirements.

Application Examples

The following section use selected application examples to show how the Reference Architecture forms added value. Efficient control solutions, dynamic order processing and the seamless integration of modern AI applications demonstrate how processes can be optimised in the long term.

Modular Design and Implementation of the Reference Architecture: Production Island_PHUKET

The production island_PHUKET is a prime example of the implementation of the Reference Architecture described above (see Figure 4). _PHUKET consists of a total of five modular encapsulated production modules, which can be individually configured via standardised hardware and software interfaces. The five production modules are divided into a storage module, two assembly modules, a laser module and a central handling module in the middle, which transports products to the individual cells. The following explanation of the Reference Architecture is divided into two sections. First, the example of a production module is used to explain how a Smart Machine Interface can be created using edge devices. Next, a production example is used to show how the product controls manufacturing independently.

Figure 4: Representation of the production island_PHUKET

Implementation of a Smart Machine

At _PHUKET, a production unit becomes a smart machine by outsourcing the control logic to an edge device. Figure 5 shows the components of an assembly module that assembles products in combination with the worker. This assembly module has a robot including a gripper for delivering products, RFID reader for identifying products in the warehouse, and a classic PLC for implementing safety-critical aspects. The robot is equipped with its own app-based control unit, which allows it to act as a smart machine in accordance with the architecture.

Siemens Industrial Edge¹ was used as the edge solution. Both apps from the Siemens internal app store (e.g. S7 Interface App for integrating the PLC) and individual applications (e.g. AutoID OPC UA Interface App for data access to smart RFID sensors [25], HTTP REST Interface App for controlling the gripper and gRPC Interface App for controlling the robot) can be used to integrate data from the field into the edge.

The machine control system (Smart Machine Logic Controller) was implemented in Python and is used to orchestrate other skills.

For this purpose, proprietary control options are encapsulated in atomic skills and composite skills are derived. These are now available to respond flexibly to production requests with the help of skills. The Smart Machine Interface is implemented by an OPC UA information model that combines OPC UA for Machinery [18] with the skill-based approach. To access these skills, they are referenced via the Asset Interface Description [20] of AAS. This means that the OPC UA interface is referenced in an integrated manner with the IT-based data bus.

The Product Guides Itself Through Production

For work planning, capabilities³ required by the product are derived in form of manufacturing features and are matched by offered machines' capabilities. Capabilities represent implementation-independent specification of a function that can be realized by skills [16]. AAS provides the information model for capabilities as well as the data access, but is purely reactive. Agents for resources and products serve to add an active component to the production system. Product agents accompany the product throughout the entire production process and work equally with the resource agents to enable flexible and responsive manufacturing. This is how it works:

Figure 5: Illustration of the control architecture of a smart machine

³ The CapabilityDescription submodel is standardised by the IDTA (Accessed 10.10.2025)

Product features contain a description of the individual properties. Based on these features, domain knowledge can be used to derive the capabilities required to manufacture the features. By comparing the required capabilities with the offered capabilities of the production resources, potential candidates for the respective manufacturing steps can be identified. The identified candidate groups are used to create several work plans that represent different execution options. If a product is to be manufactured, a call for proposal is started. Resource agents apply according to availability. Both global target criteria of the call for proposal (global optimisation) and local aspects (states and stored machine orders – local optimisation) are taken into account. The resource agents derive concrete skill sequences from the abstract capability descriptions, control and monitor the respective machines via the Smart Machine Interface, and transmit the execution data to the product agents. The product agents use this data to fully automate product-specific documentation, such as a PCF.

Active Participation in the Manufacturing-X Ecosystem

In order to implement the goals of the Manufacturing-X Initiative [3], cross-project collaboration between domain-specific projects is necessary. The Factory-X project [26] defines a configurable and open concept for decentralised, trustworthy and secure data exchange with the so-called MX-Port [27]. Data can be exchanged in a standardised and controlled manner across company boundaries. The MX-Port concept divides data exchange into five clearly defined levels (see Table 1). Different configurations are defined by assigning selected components to the individual layers. Potential candidates include, for example, AAS-submodels [28], OPC UA Companion specifications [29] or Dataspace Protocol [12]. The Reference Architecture illustrates how the individual layers of the MX-Port can be implemented in a company (see Figure 6).

Table 1: The layers (L) of the MX-Port [27]

Layer (L1-5)	Function
Discovery L5	... is used to find business partners, data sets (e.g. devices) or business applications.
Access & Usage Control L4	... is used to ensure that data providers can define data access and usage and restrict access to and usage of the data provided.
Gate L3	... is used to exchange data in a consistent manner.
Converter L2	... provides the semantic model for the data to be exchanged.
Adapter L1	... enables data access through an application-specific data connection.

Figure 6: Integration of the MX-Port into the SmartFactory architecture

Uniform, Interoperable Access Mechanisms with MCP in Production

Model Context Protocol (MCP) [30] is an open protocol and standard that enables AI-systems, especially Large Language Models (LLMs), to connect seamlessly with external tools, data sources and systems. Standardised and semantic information models enable LLMs to interpret context and unfold their full potential. By using a standardised machine interface with the help of OPC UA and AAS, the data is semantically described within the Reference Architecture. MCP enables LLMs to interact directly with these interfaces. This allows data to be queried using natural language. Interactions such as ‘how many parts were produced in the last hour?’ or ‘move the axis!’ are thus automated and implemented without additional effort.

AAS as an Enabler for Interoperable Knowledge Management

Many different entities are involved in the manufacturing of products, generating large amounts of data. At the same time, there is a wealth of knowledge and information about the entities and their relationships to one another. This can be mapped interoperable in the digital twins of the entities through the use of AAS. The relationships between the elements involved can also be represented in AAS.

Knowledge graphs, which fundamentally represent a network of entities, properties and their relationships, are suitable for mapping complex relationships. To ensure that the large amount of data stored and referenced in the AAS can be used efficiently, AAS are represented in the form of knowledge graphs. The two representations exist side by side and synchronise with each other. The metamodel of the AAS and its infrastructure forms the structural basis for this.

Thanks to the decentralised connection of the AAS and the powerful query options offered by graph databases, the knowledge represented can be used for various applications. First, it will be possible to send queries to the distributed system, such as ‘Is there an AGV available that can transport a product weighing 5 kg?’. The knowledge graph can either be

queried directly or, in combination with MCP, used as an input source for interaction with the user in natural language.

Furthermore, more complex analyses are possible using similarity algorithms. Here, for example, error cases that have occurred can be compared with errors from other machines. Recommendations for action that have already been established elsewhere can therefore also be used here.

Shared Production

A digital platform or decentralised production network that automatically connects clients with contract manufacturers while promoting resilient supply chains has the potential to reduce companies' procurement costs and efficiently manage order placement down to the field level. For Shared Production, companies must be interconnected, able to offer their services and communicate effectively in order to form a joint supply chain. In addition, they must be able to process and implement production requests internally. smartMA-X project [4] demonstrated how such production can be implemented.

Figure 7: Shared Production Kaiserslautern

The SmartFactory Reference Architecture now demonstrates how companies can integrate themselves into such a data ecosystem by using the AAS and connectors. Services can be offered or accessed interoperable with AAS and integrated directly into the company's internal data structure. One example of this is _PHUKET, which is part of Shared Production Kaiserslautern (see Figure 7) and a provider of services such as assembly.

Conclusion

The Reference Architecture presented offers manufacturing companies a clear framework for confidently mastering increasing market and technology pressures. It supports a consistent data strategy, enables the step-by-step modernisation of existing production environments and, through openness and scalability, creates the conditions for the integration of future key technologies.

In summary, this means:

- Competitiveness through interoperability in a platform-dominated market,
- Increased efficiency through consistent data availability and intelligent systems,
- Knowledge retention and transfer despite a shortage of skilled workers,
- and innovation potential through AI, data-based services and flexible production chains.

The application examples clearly show that the SmartFactory Reference Architecture forms a robust foundation for sustainable success in a connected, data-driven and collaborative industry. It thus provides a reference framework today and will support the sustainable transformation of industrial processes tomorrow.

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